

SELECTION OF CITY LOGISTICS DEVELOPMENT SCENARIOS BY APPLYING A HYBRID MCDM MODEL

SNEŽANA TADIĆ¹, MLADEN KRSTIĆ², ALEKSA MARAVIĆ³, MILOŠ VELJOVIĆ⁴

¹ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering, Belgrade, s.tadic@sf.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0003-4651-3699

² University of Belgrade, Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering, Belgrade, m.krstic@sf.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0002-7937-0543

³ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering, Belgrade, aleksamaravic16012002@gmail.com, 0009-0004-7188-4154

⁴ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering, Belgrade, m.veljovic@sf.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0001-8024-3296

Abstract: *The paper presents the selection process for the development of city logistics (CL) scenarios. Respecting current trends, four scenarios are defined. Each of the scenarios has certain characteristics that can be advantages or disadvantages in a comparative analysis. Given that the choice of development scenarios is influenced by several factors, their ranking in terms of different criteria requires the application of Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) methods. To solve the problem, a hybrid model was applied, which is based on a combination of fuzzy Factor Relationship (FARE) and Axial Distance-based Aggregated Measurement (ADAM) methods.*

Keywords: *City logistics, development scenario, MCDM, fuzzy FARE, ADAM.*

1. INTRODUCTION

As urban areas continue to expand and the rate of urbanization increases, logistics needs have become more diverse and random, and logistics operations have become more complicated. Therefore, an efficient and reliable system of city logistics (CL) has become an important part for promoting the economic development of cities and improving living standards (Tadić & Zečević, 2016; Zhang, 2022). The growth and development of traffic in goods, materials and freight follows the growth and development of CL.

CL research covers a wide range of issues, including storage, handling, distribution and other aspects, related to industry, trade, environment, etc. The planning of the CL system should take into account the requirements of companies, governments and residents and unite the interests of all parties to achieve a general system optimization (Tadić & Zečević, 2015). Numerous papers have dealt with the perspectives of the CL development (e.g. Taniguchi & Thompson, 2014). Also, many papers have evaluated the initiatives, concepts, scenarios and solutions of CL (Büyükközkán & Mukul, 2019; Tadić et al., 2014a; 2014b; 2018).

In this paper, the scenarios of the development of CL are presented and the process of their evaluation is carried out. Each scenario takes into account the interdependencies of the CL system and current trends (Tadić & Zečević, 2016a). Since the choice of scenarios depends on several factors, their evaluation requires the application of Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) methods. To solve the problem, a MCDM model was applied, based on a combination of fuzzy Factor Relationship (FARE) and Axial Distance-based Aggregated Measurement (ADAM) methods, which achieved the main goal and contribution of the work.

After the introduction, in the second chapter, the scenarios of the development of CL are described, and in the third, the criteria for their evaluation. In the fourth chapter, the procedure for choosing the most favorable scenario using the MCDM model is presented. Finally, concluding remarks are given.

2. CITY LOGISTICS DEVELOPMENT SCENARIOS

There are different prospects and possibilities for the future development of CL, and accordingly also potential scenarios. **Sustainable CL (A₁)**. The main cause of the negative effects of logistics on sustainability is the lack of planning activities and comprehensive, long-term CL policies (Tadić & Zečević, 2015; Kovač et al., 2022). Plans should cover the entire city, all modes of transport, all flows, respect all characteristics of the urban entity and all ecological, social and economic goals of all stakeholders (Tadić, 2014, Tadić & Zečević, 2016b). Alternative forms of transport, as well as cycle logistics, which can reduce carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions (Allen et al., 2012), as well as greenhouse gases, particles and nitrogen oxides (Assmann et

al., 2020), are gaining importance. **Autonomous CL (A_2)**. Efforts to overcome economic, sociopolitical and environmental challenges and improve the quality of life in the city led to the concept of autonomy. Innovations are of particular importance for solving the problem of home delivery, and can be seen through technologies or business models (automated and autonomous delivery systems; underground delivery; lockers, etc.). New solutions, such as autonomous vehicles, robots and drones, present the potential to improve efficiency. The main barriers and concerns of the authorities remain issues of safety and security. In addition, it is important to respect both the generators of the flow of goods (senders and receivers) and their implementers (logistics providers) when automating CL activities (Paddeu, 2023). Of particular importance in this scenario is the concept of hyper-connected CL, which is based on a greater degree of cooperation and consolidation, within and between cities. Research indicates the potential advantages of the concept, but also the need to make it more precise and comprehensive (Crainic et al., 2023). **Current state of CL (A_3)**. City deliveries are short, frequent, smaller in volume and contain more items (Tadić & Zečević, 2016b). More and more home deliveries are being made with little or no optimization, in a fragmented way (Attard, 2023). Many local governments still ignore CL in urban planning (Cui et al., 2015). Some of the main problems of realizing flows in the city, such as (Giuliano et al., 2013): air pollution, traffic congestion, reduced mobility and noise, are the result of inadequate logistics planning (Tadić & Zečević, 2015). Deliveries are made by operators and other organizations, as well as private individuals. However, policy makers tend to ignore such developments. A large number of CL initiatives and solutions have been defined and tested, but decisions are made ad hoc, partially, so the effects are limited (Tadić & Zečević, 2016b). One of the more recent initiatives is the integration of freight and passenger transport (Nocera et al., 2023; Tadić et al., 2022), but the most common of the initiatives are regulations, and those based on bans and fines. **Human-centered CL (A_4)**. Considering the development tendencies of various natural and anthropogenic crises, logistics "tailored to man", with a humane, resilient and even humanitarian character, may have greater importance and representation in the future, among other things in CL. It is especially important to improve the coordination of information exchange during disasters/crises (Mohammed Zain et al., 2023; Tadić et al., 2025). A more intensive development of healthcare logistics, which is very complex, is also needed (Tadić et al., 2015). Solutions such as consolidation centers can contribute to the reduction of congestion in hospitals, the optimal use of space, better service, etc. (Breen et al., 2023). Cities, especially megacities, also face other problems of existence, including food supply and poor air quality online channels play a role ("click and collect", digital platforms, mobile applications, as well as "ghost kitchens and dark stores").

3. CRITERIA FOR THE EVALUATION OF CITY LOGISTICS DEVELOPMENT SCENARIOS

There are different indicators of urban sustainability (Fehr et al., 2004), so it is possible to evaluate CL scenarios from the point of view of a large number of criteria. In this work, it was done on the basis of nine criteria that depict all aspects of sustainability (social, economic and ecological), which were chosen based on previous research (Tadić et al., 2014a; 2014b; 2018).

Mobility (C_1) refers to the movement of passenger and freight vehicles in the city. With increasing mobility, the quality of life in the city also improves. **Accessibility (C_2)** refers to the ability to access shipping/delivery locations. **Occupation/release of public space (C_3)** refers to the occupation of public areas or the possibility of their release in favor of some more attractive content. **Safety (C_4)** implies the improvement of traffic conditions, which are a consequence of the reduction in the number of delivery vehicles. **Investments (C_5)** refer to financial investments necessary for the implementation and implementation of the CL scenario. **The possibility of implementation (C_6)** refers to the complexity of administrative, regulatory, organizational, socio-cultural and other issues that accompany the implementation of a certain scenario. **Modal redistribution of transport work (C_7)** assesses the impact of scenarios on the use of alternative modes of transport. **The complexity of the implementation of the logistics chain (C_8)** depends on the degree of transformation of commodity flows. Certain scenarios transform distribution chains into multi-echelon systems, making them more complex to implement. **The environmental aspect (C_9)** is focused on reducing the negative impact of logistics activities on the environment. This refers to the reduction of fuel consumption, traffic congestion, harmful emissions into the air, emissions of noise and vibrations.

4. SELECTION OF CITY LOGISTICS DEVELOPMENT SCENARIOS

To solve the problem, a model consisting of two methods will be used, fuzzy FARE for determining the weight of criteria (Ginevičius, 2011) and ADAM for ranking of alternatives (Krstić et al., 2023).

Step 1: Defining the structure of the problem. Sets of alternatives and criteria for their evaluation are established, which was done in previous chapters.

Step 2: Defining scales for evaluating criteria and alternatives. The importance of criteria and alternatives is described by linguistic evaluations that are transformed into triangular fuzzy numbers (TFN) (in the case of the fuzzy FARE), i.e. crisp numerical values (in the case of the ADAM): None: N, (1, 1, 2), 1; Very low: VL, (1, 2, 3), 2; Low: L, (2, 3, 4), 3; Fairly low: FL, (3, 4, 5), 4; Medium: M, (4, 5, 6), 5; Fairly high: FH, (5, 6, 7), 6; High: H, (6, 7, 8), 7; Very high: VH, (7, 8, 9), 8; Extremely high: EH, (8, 9, 10), 9.

Step 3: Obtaining criterion weights.

Step 3.1: First, on the basis of the author's expert knowledge, experience and insight into the relevant literature (e.g. Tadić, 2014; Taniguchi, 2014; Zhang, 2022), linguistic evaluations of the criteria comparison (Table 1) were assigned, which are converted into TFN. This way of describing the relationship between the importance of the criteria is the most adequate because the fuzzy environment can adequately deal with ambiguity, inaccuracies and ambiguities in assessments. A matrix is created for evaluating the criteria \tilde{A} .

$$\tilde{A} = [\tilde{a}_{ij}]_{n \times n} \quad (1)$$

where $\tilde{a}_{ij} = (l, m, u) = (l, m, n)$ is the evaluation of the importance of criterion i in relation to criterion j . Items l, m i u are the lower, middle and upper value of TFNs; n is the number of criteria; and the following applies:

$$\tilde{a}_{ji} = -\tilde{a}_{ij} \quad (2)$$

and evaluation is considered consistent if:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n u = -\sum_{j=1}^n l \quad (3)$$

Table 1: Input and output data for the fuzzy FARE method

	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	Crisp weight
C ₁		H								0,881
C ₂										0,806
C ₃	FH	M		FH			FH	M		1,108
C ₄	M	FH					M			0,979
C ₅	EH	VH	H	H		L	FL	VL	L	1,269
C ₆	VH	H	H	H			FH	N	L	1,230
C ₇	H	FH						FL		0,993
C ₈	VH	H		FH					VL	1,069
C ₉	FH	FH	M	M			L			1,084

Step 3.2: Obtaining the potential impact of criteria \tilde{P} :

$$\tilde{P} = H(n - 1) \quad (4)$$

where H s the highest value of the scale used for estimations.

Step 3.3: Obtaining the overall impact (importance) of the criteria \tilde{P}_j :

$$\tilde{P}_j = \sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{a}_{ij}, \forall j = 1, \dots, n; j \neq i \quad (5)$$

Step 3.4: Obtaining the final weights of fuzzy criteria (Table 1):

$$W = \frac{\tilde{P}_j}{\tilde{P}_H}, \forall j = 1, \dots, n \quad (6)$$

where \tilde{P}_H is the total potential importance of the obtained criteria:

$$\tilde{P}_H = \left(\min_j l^{\tilde{P}_j r}, \text{mean } m^{\tilde{P}_j r}, \max_j u^{\tilde{P}_j r} \right) \quad (7)$$

where P_j s the actual total impact of the criteria j :

$$\tilde{P}_j^r = \tilde{P}_j + \tilde{P}, \forall j = 1, \dots, n \quad (8)$$

Step 4: Ranking of alternatives using the ADAM method.

Step 4.1: Define the matrix E . Elements are the evaluation e_{qj} of the alternative q according to criterion j :

$$E = [e_{qj}]_{m \times n} \quad (9)$$

where m is the number of alternatives, and n is the number of criteria (Table 2). The grades, as in the case of the weights of the criteria, are defined on the basis of the author's knowledge and research experience.

Step 4.2: Define a sorted decision matrix S whose elements s_{qj} are sorted ratings e_{qj} decreasing according to the importance (weight) of the criteria:

$$S = [s_{qj}]_{m \times n} \quad (10)$$

Step 4.3: Define a normalized sorted matrix N whose elements are n_{qj} normalized scores:

$$n_{qj} = \begin{cases} \frac{s_{qj}}{\max_q s_{qj}}, & \text{for } j \in B \\ \frac{\min_q s_{qj}}{s_{qj}}, & \text{for } j \in C \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where B is a set of benefit criteria, and C is a set of cost criteria.

Step 4.4: Find the coordinates (x, y, z) of the reference (R_{qj}) and difficult reference (P_{qj}) points that define the complex polyhedron:

$$x_{qj} = n_{qj} \times \sin \alpha_j, \forall j = 1, \dots, n; \forall q = 1, \dots, m \quad (12)$$

$$y_{qj} = n_{qj} \times \cos \alpha_j, \forall j = 1, \dots, n; \forall q = 1, \dots, m \quad (13)$$

$$z_{qj} = \begin{cases} 0, \text{ za } R_{qj} \\ w_j, \text{ za } O_{qj} \end{cases}, \forall j = 1, \dots, n; \forall q = 1, \dots, m \quad (14)$$

where α_j is the angle that determines the direction of the vector that defines the value of the alternative:

$$\alpha_j = (j - 1) \frac{90^\circ}{n - 1}, \forall j = 1, \dots, n \quad (15)$$

Step 4.5: Find the volumes of complex polyhedra V_q^C :

$$V_q^C = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} V_k, \forall q = 1, \dots, m \quad (16)$$

where V_k is the volumes of the pyramids of which it is composed:

$$V_k = \frac{1}{3} B_k \times h_k, \forall k = 1, \dots, n - 1 \quad (17)$$

where B_k is the area of the base of the pyramid defined by the reference and difficult reference points of two consecutive criteria:

$$B_k = c_k \times a_k + \frac{a_k \times (b_k - c_k)}{2} \quad (18)$$

a_k is the Euclidean distance between the reference points of two consecutive criteria that is obtained:

$$a_k = \sqrt{(x_{j+1} - x_j)^2 + (y_{j+1} - y_j)^2} \quad (19)$$

b_k and c_k are vector intensities corresponding to the weights of two consecutive criteria:

$$b_k = z_j \quad (20)$$

$$c_k = z_{j+1} \quad (21)$$

h is the height of the pyramid from the base to the top of the pyramid located in the coordinate origin (O):

$$h_k = \frac{2\sqrt{s_k(s_k - a_k)(s_k - d_k)(s_k - e_k)}}{a_k} \quad (22)$$

where s_k is the semicircumference of the triangle defined by the x coordinates of two consecutive criteria and the coordinate origin:

$$s_k = \frac{a_k + d_k + e_k}{2} \quad (23)$$

where d_k and e_k are the Euclidean distances of reference points of two consecutive criteria from the coordinate origin:

$$d_k = \sqrt{x_j^2 + y_j^2} \quad (24)$$

$$e_k = \sqrt{x_{j+1}^2 + y_{j+1}^2} \quad (25)$$

Step 5: Rank the alternatives according to the decreasing values of the volumes V_q^C ($q = 1, \dots, m$). The ranking of alternatives was performed using ADAM 1.2-beta software (<http://adam-mcdm.com>).

Table 2: Input and output data for the ADAM method

	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	Volume	Rank
A ₁	8	2	4	7	3	2	9	3	9	0,3575	1
A ₂	2	4	7	2	2	3	1	4	6	0,1804	2
A ₃	5	8	2	6	7	8	5	6	3	0,1339	4
A ₄	3	6	8	4	5	5	3	2	4	0,1691	3

The best-rated alternative is sustainable CL. The implementation of this scenario, although demanding in terms of investment and accompanying regulations, is expected to reconcile the often conflicting interests of stakeholders. The implementation of logistics services would be more efficient, the traffic network would be relieved, environmentally friendly modes of transport would be promoted, urban residents would be guaranteed to achieve environmental quality, etc.

5. CONCLUSION

Cities develop and change, and with that, CL. This development may lead to different scenarios in the future, and which one will prevail is not easy to assess. In this paper, the answer to this question was given using two methods, fuzzy FARE and ADAM. Development of CL in the direction of sustainability, was chosen as the most favorable solution. Bearing in mind the world's social and natural challenges, it is highly expected and desirable that CL develops in this direction. This scenario was chosen as a compromise solution because it provides an opportunity for the development of such a CL system which, in addition to increasing the efficiency of the implementation of logistics activities, also respects the needs of the community, which in most cases are related to improving the quality of life. In the context of future research, papers dealing with this topic could analyze the defined scenarios in more detail. In addition, the MCDM model could be extended to include a larger number of criteria or perspectives from different stakeholders.

LITERATURE

- Allen, J., Browne, M., Woodburn, A., & Leonardi, J. (2012). The Role of Urban Consolidation Centres in Sustainable Freight Transport, *Transport Reviews*, 32(4), 473–490.
- Assmann, T., Lang, S., Müller, F., & Schenk, M. (2020). Impact assessment model for the implementation of cargo bike transshipment points in urban districts, *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(10), 4082–4101.
- Attard, M. (2023). Climate Change and Urban Logistics. In Monios, J., Budd, L., & Ison, S. (Eds.), *The Routledge Handbook of Urban Logistics* (323–332), Routledge.
- Breen, L., Schiffing, S., & Xie, Y. (2023). Healthcare and Urban Logistics. In Monios, J., Budd, L., & Ison, S. (Eds.), *The Routledge Handbook of Urban Logistics* (159–174), Routledge.

- Büyüközkan, G., & Mukul, E. (2019). Evaluation of smart city logistics solutions with fuzzy MCDM methods, *Pamukkale Üniversitesi Mühendislik Bilimleri Dergisi*, 25(9), 1033–1040.
- Crainic, T. G., Klibi, W., & Montreuil, B. (2023). Hyperconnected city logistics: a conceptual framework. In Marcucci, E., Gatta, V., & Le Pira, M. (Eds.), *Handbook on City Logistics and Urban Freight* (398–421), Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Cui, J., Dodson, J., & Hall, P.V. (2015). Planning for urban freight transport: An overview, *Transport Reviews*, 35(5), 583–598.
- Fehr, M., Alves de Sousa, K., Pereira, A., & Pelizer, L. (2004). Proposal of Indicators to assess urban sustainability in Brazil, *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 6(3), 355–366.
- Ginevičius, R. (2011). A new determining method for the criteria weights in multicriteria evaluation. *International Journal of Information Technology & Decision Making*, 10(6), 1067–1095.
- Giuliano, G., O'Brien, T., Dablanc, L., & Holliday, K. (2013). *Synthesis Of Freight Research In Urban Transportation Planning*, NCFRP Report 23, Washington DC.
- Kovač, M., Tadić, S., & Krstić, M. (2022). Planning and development of sustainable logistics systems at a micro-level, *Tehnika*, 69(2), 225–231.
- Krstić, M., Agnusdei, G.P., Tadić, S., Kovač, M., & Miglietta, P.P. (2023). A Novel Axial-Distance-Based Aggregated Measurement (ADAM) Method for the Evaluation of Agri-Food Circular-Economy-Based Business Models. *Mathematics*, 11(6).
- Mohammed Zain, R., Mohd Zahari, H., & Mohd Zainol N.A. (2023). Inter-agency information sharing coordination on humanitarian logistics support for urban disaster management in Kuala Lumpur, *Frontiers Sustainable Cities*, vol. 5.
- Paddeu, D. (2023). New technologies and autonomous vehicles for urban goods distribution. In Marcucci, E., Gatta, V., & Le Pira, M. (Eds.), *Handbook on City Logistics and Urban Freight* (444–462), Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Tadić, S. (2014). *Integrated city logistics solutions performance modelling*. University of Belgrade, Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering, PhD thesis [in Serbian].
- Tadić, S., & Zečević, S. (2015). Integrated planning aimed at sustainability city logistics solutions, *Tehnika*, 65(1), 164–173.
- Tadić, S., & Zečević, S. (2016a). Global trends and their impact on city logistics management, *Tehnika*, 71(3), 459–464.
- Tadić, S., & Zečević, S. (2016b). *Modelling city logistics concepts*. Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering, Belgrade [in Serbian].
- Tadić, S., Veljović, M., & Zečević, S. (2022). Crowd logistics: household as a logistics service provider, *International Journal for Traffic and Transport Engineering*, 12(1), 111–122.
- Tadić, S., Veljović, M., Krstić, M., & Zečević, S. (2025). Humanitarian logistics: a framework for structuring and research, *Transportation Research Procedia*, 21th international conference on transport science, ICTS 2024, Portoroz, Slovenia, 20-21.05. 2024, 83, 72–79 [in Serbian].
- Tadić, S., Zečević, S., & Krstić, M. (2014a). A novel hybrid MCDM model based on fuzzy DEMATEL, fuzzy ANP and fuzzy VIKOR for city logistics concept selection, *Expert Systems with Application*, 18, 8112–8128.
- Tadić, S., Zečević, S., & Krstić, M. (2014b). Ranking of logistics system scenarios for central business district, *Promet-Traffic & Transportation*, 26(2), 159–167.
- Tadić, S., Zečević, S., & Krstić, M. (2018). Assessment of the political city logistics initiatives sustainability, *Transportation Research Procedia*, 30, 285–294.
- Taniguchi, E. (2014). Concepts of city logistics for sustainable and liveable cities. *Procedia-social and behavioral sciences*, 151, 310-317.
- Taniguchi, E., & Thompson, R. G. (Eds.). (2014). *City logistics: Mapping the future*. CRC Press.
- Zhang, H. (2022). *Reliability Optimization of Urban Logistics Systems*. Springer.